

Komite Etik Penelitian *Research Ethics Committee*

Surat Layak Etik *Research Ethics Approval*

No:005048/KEP STIKES SUKABUMI/2025

Peneliti Utama : Asmarawanti
Principal Investigator

Peneliti Anggota : -
Member Investigator

Nama Lembaga : STIKes Sukabumi
Name of The Institution

Judul : Terjemahan dan Validasi Versi Indonesia dari Skala Penilaian Pengetahuan tentang Perkembangan Bayi (KIDI) di kalangan orang tua di Indonesia
Title
Translation and Validation of the Indonesian Version of the Knowledge of Infant Development Inventory (KIDI) Scale among parent in Indonesia

Atas nama Komite Etik Penelitian (KEP), dengan ini diberikan surat layak etik terhadap usulan protokol penelitian, yang didasarkan pada 7 (tujuh) Standar dan Pedoman WHO 2011, dengan mengacu pada pemenuhan Pedoman CIOMS 2016 (lihat lampiran). *On behalf of the Research Ethics Committee (REC), I hereby give ethical approval in respect of the undertakings contained in the above mention research protocol. The approval is based on 7 (seven) WHO 2011 Standard and Guidance part III, namely Ethical Basis for Decision-making with reference to the fulfilment of 2016 CIOMS Guideline (see enclosed).*

Kelayakan etik ini berlaku satu tahun efektif sejak tanggal penerbitan, dan usulan perpanjangan diajukan kembali jika penelitian tidak dapat diselesaikan sesuai masa berlaku surat kelayakan etik. Perkembangan kemajuan dan selesainya penelitian, agar dilaporkan. *The validity of this ethical clearance is one year effective from the approval date. You will be required to apply for renewal of ethical clearance on a yearly basis if the study is not completed at the end of this clearance. You will be expected to provide mid progress and final reports upon completion of your study. It is your responsibility to ensure that all researchers associated with this project are aware of the conditions of approval and which documents have been approved.*

Setiap perubahan dan alasannya, termasuk indikasi implikasi etis (jika ada), kejadian tidak diinginkan serius (KTD/KTDS) pada partisipan dan tindakan yang diambil untuk mengatasi efek tersebut; kejadian tak terduga lainnya atau perkembangan tak terduga yang perlu diberitahukan; ketidakmampuan untuk perubahan lain dalam personel penelitian yang terlibat dalam proyek, wajib dilaporkan. *You require to notify of any significant change and the reason for that change, including an indication of ethical implications (if any); serious adverse effects on participants and the action taken to address those effects; any other unforeseen events or unexpected developments that merit notification; the inability to any other change in research personnel involved in the project.*

Masa berlaku:
15 October 2025 - 15 October 2026

15 October 2025
Chair Person

Hana Haryani

Resume Penilaian

Resume Assessment

Study title: "Translation and Validation of the Indonesian Version of the Knowledge of Infant Development Inventory (KIDI) Scale among parent in Indonesia.

1. Research Justification and Background

Parents' knowledge of the baby's development is essential for fostering cognitive, emotional, and physical abilities. Although important, Indonesia still lacks culturally validated tools to comprehensively assess childcare knowledge. Knowledge of Inventory Infant Development (KIDI), which is widely used internationally, has not been psychometrically evaluated in the Indonesian context.

Rationale: Despite the availability of this developmental assessment tool, Indonesia does not yet have a validated instrument specifically designed to measure parents' knowledge of infant development. Research underscores the importance of parenting knowledge in shaping self-perception among children. New mothers and their influence on parenting stress

Theoretical Framework: This study focuses on validating Indonesia's adaptation of the Knowledge of Infant Development Inventory (KIDI) Questionnaire.

Potential Benefits: This study aims to translate, culturally adapt, and validate the Indonesian version of KIDI to assess construct validity, reliability, and structural integrity among parents of children aged 0–6 years.

2. Formulation of Research Objectives and Questions

Objective: to translate, culturally adapt, and validate the Indonesian version of KIDI to assess construct validity, reliability, and structural integrity among parents of children aged 0–6 years.

Research Question: How to translate, culturally adapt, and validate the Indonesian version of KIDI to assess construct validity, reliability, and structural integrity among parents of children aged 0–6 years.

3. Research Methods

Type of Study: This study used a cross-sectional design

Population: This study involved parents of children aged 0–6 years who were recruited from various regions throughout Indonesia. Both mother and father were included in the sample to improve the generalization of the results

Object: This study involved parents of children aged 0–6 years who were recruited from various regions throughout Indonesia. Both mother and father were included in the sample to improve the generalization of the results

4. Subject Recruitment Procedure

Inclusion Criteria: parents aged 18 years and above with children aged 0–6 years. They need to have the ability to read and understand Indonesian and give informed consent to participate in this research

Exclusion Criteria: Parents have cognitive or psychological conditions that may hinder their understanding or ability to complete questionnaires. In addition, those who have participated in similar validation studies are also excluded to prevent potential bias in the findings.

Persuasion: There is no element of coercion or exploitation. Participation is **voluntary** and based on **informed consent**. Participants will be given a thorough explanation of their objectives, procedures, and rights to refuse or terminate participation at any time without consequences.

5. Data Collection Methods

Instrument: Knowledge of Infant Development Inventory (KIDI)

Method: Data collection was carried out through a questionnaire

Data Analysis: Data analysis using SPSS and AMOS

Data Encryption: Data will be managed electronically **and encrypted** to ensure security.

6. Ethical Issues, Risks, and Participant Protection

Ethical Issues: There were no risks in this study

Potential Risks: There were no risks in this study